

PROPORTION DANCING FOR MATERIALLY ENACTED COVARIATIONAL REASONING

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This paper presents part of a design-based research study that explores 5th-grade students' materially enactments of covariation while using a motion-tracking technology called 'MaLT2Dance' to create "dancing" dynamic shapes. Eight students collaborated in pairs to choreograph the shape of a tetris-like letter "L" on screen by dynamically transforming its side lengths. They controlled two parameters' values linked to two sides of the shape – that remained "closed" only when the ratio of 1:2 was satisfied – through hand gestures in order to animate the shape in harmony with selected songs. The analysis traced how students' initially uncoordinated movement gradually evolved into increasingly refined, materially enacted covariation guided by their aesthetic perception of what visual-dynamic form better fits the song. The discussion highlights how this environment supported the emergence of different types of materially enacted, aesthetically-driven covariational reasoning.

Keywords: Covariational reasoning, enactment, motion-capture technology, aesthetics, dance.

INTRODUCTION

Covariational reasoning is widely acknowledged as a fundamental component of functional thinking, involving the capacity to simultaneously coordinate changes between two interdependent quantities (Carlson et al., 2002; Thompson & Carlson, 2017). Nevertheless, typical classroom practice continues to privilege static forms of expression (printed graphs, tables, worked examples), detached from the embodied, sensory, and affective dimensions integral to learners' mathematical experience (De Freitas & Sinclair, 2014; Shvarts & van Helden, 2023). Although digital technologies have provided opportunities to interact dynamically with mathematical structures, most current research continues to prioritize verbal and symbolic expressions of covariation, positioning the body instrumentally rather than as an active source of mathematical meaning-making (Basu & Panorkou, 2019; Pitalis et al., 2024). Moreover, empirical work commonly centers on structured, physics/simulation-based tasks, limiting exploration into open-ended or aesthetically-guided experiences.

The present study investigates alternative modalities of covariational reasoning through embodied choreographic engagement, situating learners' bodily movement and aesthetic judgments (of "what better fits the song") at the core of the mathematical activity. Specifically, it examines how fifth-grade students employed the MaLT2Dance digital environment; a motion-tracking-based technology enabling users to control parameters values linked to geometric transformations through hand movements. Within this environment, students choreographed dynamic geometric shapes (tetris-like letters) to synchronize and "match" their movements with musical structures, exploring proportional relationships and covariation through enactments of coordinated gestures. The epistemological roots of this work is grounded in new materialist perspectives (De Freitas & Sinclair, 2014), which emphasizes mathematics learning as emergent from the entanglement of bodies, digital tools, and mathematical structures. Building upon previous studies conducted with older students involving choreographing geometric animations in the MaLT2 environment without motion recognition (Karavakou & Kynigos, 2023; 2025), this study incorporates motion-tracking technology to enrich embodied expression of mathematical ideas from younger learners. This paper

addresses the research question: What forms of enactments of covariational reasoning do fifth-grade students develop in an aesthetically-guided context involving the synchronization of dynamic geometric shapes with music? In reconceptualizing covariational reasoning as aesthetically-driven and embodied, this research seeks to illustrate how meanings on covariation emerge through rhythmic synchronization, embodied coordination, peer collaboration, and affective engagement – challenging traditional views centered predominantly on symbolic and discursive expressions. Ultimately, this study aims to contribute to an emerging discourse in mathematics education that foregrounds material, embodied, and aesthetic dimensions of mathematical reasoning.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Covariational reasoning (CR) has been extensively studied as mental actions involving the envision of simultaneous changes between two quantities, particularly within contexts of graphs sketching and interpretation (Basu & Panorkou, 2019; Carlson et al., 2002; Thompson & Carlson, 2017). Thompson and Carlson (2017) identified six developmental levels of CR: (L0) *absence of coordination*, where learners have no image of variables-quantities varying together; (L1) *pre-coordination*, involving recognition of two variables' values varying, but asynchronously; (L2) *gross coordination*, involving the formation of a gross image of quantities' values varying together, with respect to direction of change; (L3) *coordination of values*, where they track correspondences between pairs of values; (L4) *chunky continuous covariation*, where they envision changes dynamically but segmentally – corresponding intervals of variable-quantity values; and (L5) *smooth continuous covariation*, where they envision simultaneous changes of the two variable-quantity values fluently and continuously. Most approaches adhering to this framework primarily focus on students' verbal or symbolic-algebraic expressions of covariation, grounding mathematical thought in internal representational processes, thus maintaining a mental-centric stance (Basu & Panorkou, 2019; Pitalis et al., 2024).

Initial attempts to incorporate embodiment into CR introduced the concept of *embodied instrumented covariation* (Bagossi, 2024; Ferretti et al., 2024), positioning bodily action and digital tool use as means for supporting the conceptualization of covariation. Despite recognizing embodiment, this perspective treats the body instrumentally, mobilized in the service of pre-defined cognitive goals; e.g., of reaching a smooth image of covariation through verbal reflection. This study is theoretically differentiated as it adopts a new materialist perspective (Barad, 2003; De Freitas & Sinclair, 2014), re-framing CR as *materially enacted* and *aesthetically-driven*, where learning emerges through the dynamic intra-actions of bodies, sensory perceptions, aesthetic judgements, digital tools, and mathematical structures (Karavakou & Kynigos, 2025; Latsi & Kynigos, 2022). This perspective does not assume fixed cognitive endpoints; instead, it allows meaning to emerge through open-ended engagement with materials and sensations. In this context, material enactment involves the ongoing and affectively charged emergence of meaning through bodily movement, sensory perception and attunement (e.g., to aesthetic fit or harmony), and material conditions (e.g., musical rhythm, melody, or the simulated covariation afforded by the digital tool), without being confined to predetermined representational forms (Sinclair et al., 2013). Such an approach re-theorizes CR, by opening up broader ways for students to feel, sense, and enact covariation. Here, mathematical relationships are experienced not as abstract algebraic entities but as perceptually harmonious or dissonant forms. Covariation is thus co-constructed as an integral component of artistic and mathematical expression, emphasizing the inseparability of cognitive, embodied, affective, and aesthetic dimensions in learners' mathematical experiences.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a design-based research (DBR) methodology in order to explore the emergence of materially enacted, aesthetically-driven CR in activities involving the choreography of digital dynamic figures using motion-capture technology. The first (precedent) DBR cycle surfaced usability issues leading to technological improvements. The main second cycle took place in the context of a school-based intervention involving eight fifth-grade students (aged 10–11), four of whom were girls. The intervention lasted for six teaching hours and was implemented during the regular school schedule in collaboration with the classroom teacher. Students worked in pairs, each sharing a computer and a pair of headphones. The activities were designed within the MaLT2Dance environment (<https://extendt2.com/widgets/malt2dance/>), an extension of MaLT2 (<http://etl.ppp.uoa.gr/malt2/>) featuring integrated hand-tracking technology that links real-time hand motion to the dynamic manipulation of parameter sliders through a webcam. In the activities, each student pair was prompted to synchronize their hand movements to control two parameters (α -alpha and β -beta) in order to maintain geometric letters (such as the letter “L”) in balanced or unbalanced configurations, while making them “dance” in alignment with musical pieces (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Examples-screenshots of balanced or unbalanced configurations of the “L” shape

This paper focuses on the first part of the designed activities, which lasted two teaching hours. During this phase, the dynamic representation of the letter “L” was defined by the proportional relation $\alpha = 2\beta$. Students were encouraged to animate the letter in synchrony with selected background songs by moving their hands in three distinct ways, corresponding to three phases: (1) one student controlled the α -slider with one hand, while the other controlled the β -slider using the mouse, and then they switched roles; (2) one student controlled β with one hand, while the other used the mouse for α , and then switched; and (3) both students controlled one slider each using one hand. In the first two phases, students were prompted to explore a “break-and-fix” sequence of choreographed imbalance and restoration to match the musical rhythm. In the third phase, students were free to develop their own movement patterns.

Figure 2. The three distinct ways of moving the sliders with one-hand-and-mouse or two-hands movement (video can be seen by clicking on this [link](#) or by scanning the QR code in the picture).

Data were collected using multiple sources: video recordings of all groups at intervals, screen recordings (with audio), voice recordings for each group, student worksheets/notes, researchers' journals, and semi-structured interviews focused on moments students found confusing or harmonious. Data analysis followed a thematic approach, coding hand/mouse movement captured in screen recordings and videos, discourse, and notes. The goal was an initial attempt to identify the way students enacted CR through their material-aesthetic engagement with the technology and trace links with the developmental levels described by Thompson & Carlson (2017). Thus, our initial deductive codebook was seeded by this framework and expanded inductively to capture embodied/choreographic moves that supported this type of CR. Critical episodes were analyzed as cases of aesthetically-driven CR enactment, loosely mapped to the six-level model. In the next section, selected critical episodes from the first and third phases are presented and discussed.

RESULTS

Hand–Mouse Asynchronous Coordination: "Break–Fix, Break–Fix..."

In the beginning of the activity (prior to enabling the hand-tracking camera), students could only manipulate parameter sliders using the mouse. At this stage, one of the researchers posed the question: "Do you notice any relationship between α and β when the L-shape is closed?" (referring to the balanced configuration). All groups responded verbally that "alpha is double beta" (G1, G2, G4) or "beta is half of alpha" (G3). Despite articulating this relationship early on, coordinated action between group members – where one student manipulated the α -parameter with their hand and the other controlled β using the mouse (first phase) – remained uncoordinated, aligning with L0 (*absence of coordination*) in Thompson and Carlson's (2017) model.

Once students agreed on their roles in the first phase (hand-mouse asynchronous coordination), the student using their hand began by "breaking" the closed shape through changes in α value, while the one with the mouse attempted to "fix" it by adjusting the β value. In three out of the four groups, hand and mouse movements initially followed opposite directions adopting a trial-and-error approach, where feedback from the dynamic shape (whether or how it approached a balanced state) prompted adjustments. For example, in the first song, one student (S1) in Group 1 (G1) began by dragging the α -slider leftward to $\alpha = 26$, while the other student (S2) initially moved β from 86 to 151 (rightward), thereby "breaking" the shape further (first 3 seconds of the video in Figure 3a). S2 then reversed direction and adjusted β to 13 to "repair" the shape (next 2 seconds). Initially, S2's actions reflected *absence of coordination* (L0) type of reasoning, failing to coordinate movements

to restore balance. However, throughout the remainder of the video, S2 began each fixing attempt in the correct direction, gradually approaching the target value through approximations, suggestive of L1 (*pre-coordination*) and L2 (*gross coordination*) reasoning. This evolving practice, guided by the feedback from the shape and shaped by S1's disruptive hand motion, exemplifies the distributed and emergent nature of covariational expression. After four such "break-fix" choreographies to the same song (totaling 336 seconds), G1 demonstrated an enacted CR consistent with L3 (*coordination of values*). Before the fifth round, the following exchange occurred:

Student 1: Did you get how we'll do it? With each change, follow the notes. When they go up, we go up. You just follow me.

Student 2: Ok.

As observed in the video (Figure 3b), their new choreography was an attempt to enact this idea through delayed-synchronized covariation. Compared to earlier footage (Figure 3a), both students expressed shifting modes of enacting covariation: S1 adjusted the amplitude, rate, and direction of hand movement in accordance with musical cues, while S2 followed with the mouse at half the rate. Their adjustments, although not simultaneous, converged toward satisfying the relationship $\alpha = 2\beta$ to "restore" the balanced shape. These actions suggest materially enacted refinements in coordination linked to elements from L3 (*coordination of values*) and L4 (*chunky continuous coordination*) as movements became more stable and directed. At times, changes even occurred almost simultaneously, with β moving through half the interval of α . However, the following exchange reveals that students were unable to verbalize the difference in movement rates:

Researcher: You're making it dance so well! How did you manage that?

Student 1: We followed the music. And [S2] followed me.

Researcher: And when you follow [S1], what exactly do you do?

Student 2: I go where he goes.

Researcher: What do you mean by that?

Student 2: I do the same movement.

Figure 3. Videos of hand-and-mouse moving along with the music from G1's (3a) initial ([link](#)) and (3b) final ([link](#)) engagement with the activity from the first phase.

By the end of the two phases, in which all students had alternated between using hand and mouse control for the two parameter values, none explicitly articulated verbally the covarying relationship underpinning transitions from one state of balance to another. Still, their embodied delayed-synchronization gave rise to evolving patterns of enacted CR similar to the one described above. In addition, the "break-fix" choreographic pattern was persistent across all groups despite prompts to design their own choreographic ideas towards the end of each phase.

Two-Hands Synchronous Coordination: “Follow the Melody together”

In the third phase, both members of each group controlled the parameters using one hand each. This configuration led to new, differentiated forms of materially enacted CR that followed similar emergent patterns of reasoning, as observed in three groups (G1, G3, and G4). The following critical episodes come from G4 and illustrate three distinct types of materially enacted CR, each emerged during a shared choreographic idea: the dynamic L-shape should expand and contract to the rhythm of the music while remaining continuously closed (in balance). The first type of reasoning was characterized by an attempt to synchronize both parameters (α and β) through simultaneous hand movements aligned with the rhythm (video in Figure 4a). Students S7 and S8, each controlled one parameter: S7 controlled β with her left hand (orange-coloured hand), and S8 controlled α with her right hand (purple-coloured hand). As seen in the video, both hands moved in the same direction and at the same tempo for each increase (rightward) or decrease (leftward) in values and overall shape size. However, after each simultaneous movement, the resulting β -value failed to maintain the balance condition ($\alpha = 2\beta$). S8 then hold her hand steady and verbally prompted S7 to move “up” or “down” to restore the shape before continuing. S7 used these metaphors to refer to the direction of change that S8 needed to continue doing in order to get to the balance state. These coordinated, rhythm-driven movements indicate development of *gross coordination* (L2), as they were enacting the directional co-change within each movement, but they kept changing the parameters’ values with the exact same rate.

This tactic led to a transition phase in G4’s engagement, as the group recognized the *non-smooth* coordination of the two quantities and sought to “practice” for *smoother coordination*. S8 proposed: “Let’s do break-and-fix again to get it right one more time.”. In the subsequent video excerpt (Figure 4b), the students shifted from simultaneous to sequential movements, mirroring the structure of the first two phases. S8 moved the α -slider (right hand, purple), “breaking” the shape, while S7 followed by adjusting the β -slider (left hand, orange), “fixing the shape” – this time carefully attending to the numerical values shown on screen. They constructed successive (α , β) pairs that satisfied the relationship $\alpha = 2\beta$, demonstrating materially enacted covariation closer to the *coordination of values* level (L3). This shift marks a movement from the aesthetic criterion of “following the rhythm” toward the goal of achieving closure (balance) at each step.

Figure 4. Videos of hand-and-mouse moving along with the music from G4’s (4a) initial engagement ([link](#)); (4b) transition phase using sequential control ([link](#)); and (4c) Final performance showing differentiated simultaneous coordination ([link](#)) during the third phase.

The third type of reasoning observed in G4 signaled the emergence of enactments of *chunky continuous*-like covariation (L4) and, at times, even *smooth continuous*-like covariation (L5) across periods of synchronized shape modulation. This pattern developed after 15 minutes of practicing L2–L3 covariation. The students returned to simultaneous movement but began to vary the tempo

of each hand. As seen in the last video (Figure 5c), S8 (controlling α -values) moved her hand almost twice as fast as S7 (controlling β -values). This refined differentiation in movement rates indicates an emergent attunement to covariation as an affective, materially enacted rhythm of *smooth* relational coordination, shaped through the intra-action of hand-movement, sense of balance and fit to the sound. The L-shape remained consistently closed as their coordinated moves formed a harmonious choreography that embodied the rule $\alpha = 2\beta$. However, during a final interview, G4 (like all the other groups) was unable to verbally articulate the specific nature of their relational coordination:

Researcher: Did you notice any connection between the ways you moved your hands?

Student 8: It felt like one was a bit different.

Researcher: Different how?

Student 8: Sometimes one was quicker than the other, and then the other way around.

DISCUSSION

This study examined fifth-grade students' enactments of CR through embodied, aesthetically-driven engagement with dynamic geometric shapes and music, framed within a new-materialist perspective. CR emerged through materially enacted intra-actions among bodies, sounds, digital tools, and evolving aesthetic criteria. Each activity phase facilitated distinct enactments: initial mouse-hand interactions primarily elicited forms of reasoning that resembled earlier stages (L0 – L2) of Thompson and Carlson's (2017) model, characterized by asynchronous, trial-and-error movements to restore shape balance in alignment with musical rhythm. In contrast, the third phase, involving hand-hand coordination within a shared embodied space, enabled more varied and sophisticated choreographic expressions. Students moved from basic synchronized gestures toward differentiated coordination, displaying enactments aligning closely with Thompson and Carlson's higher levels (L4 – L5), such as chunky and smooth continuous covariation. However, rather than showing a linear progression through clearly delineated stages, students frequently revisited simpler enactments (e.g., L3) as productive sites of emergent complexity. These recursive enactments were integral in bridging simpler movement patterns with refined covariational coordination, highlighting that CR does not strictly evolve linearly, but through iterative, materially entangled engagements.

Throughout the activity, CR emerged through aesthetic and embodied attunements rather than verbal or symbolic articulations. Mathematical meaning was enacted through sensory perceptions of music-shape-movement harmony, hand gestures, and the material affordances of digital tools, resonating strongly with new materialist views on mathematics learning (De Freitas & Sinclair, 2014). However, the study is limited by its small sample size and short duration, highlighting the need for further implementation across diverse contexts and longer timescales to better and further conceptualize materially enacted CR.

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